

Impact of Self-Efficacy and Learning Goal Orientation on Psychological Detachment with the Mediating Role of Emotional Intelligence

Author's Details:

Rehana Kosar^{1*}, Shifa Rathore², Asadullah Khan³, Humaira Arzoo⁴, Faraset Sabir⁵

^{1,2,4} Student, Department of management Sciences, Riphah international University Rawalpindi Pakistan.

³ Student, Harbin institute of technology PR China ⁵ Student, International Islamic University Islamabad, Pakistan.

Correspondence Author: Rehanakousar21@gmail.com

Abstract

The main determination of the study is to find out the connection between self-effective and learning goal orientation in the presence of emotional intelligence and their influence on psychological detachment. The study also observes how emotional intelligence controls the connection of self-efficacy, learning goal orientation, and psychological detachment and to find out the best possible keys that may contribute to exploiting the best self-efficacy and learning goal orientation not only for emotionally smart people but for others whose emotional intelligence score is minor. The result of this study would be based on the data collected from different organizations, genders, and age groups upon worldwide agreed definitions of all the above-stated terms. The suggested study covers major emotional determinants that may affect the enactment of entities and organizations. The study covers the area of the academic sector which will help the teachers and principals to manage stress and workload. This study is also beneficial for the person who belonged to this sector. In this research, we surveyed employees working in the Pakistani educational sector and focused on the psychological detachment of teachers and Principals. Among the total usable responses, 243(70%) were used through quantitative research methodology and interpreted results through SPSS. The results show that self-efficacy and learning goal orientation significantly influence psychological detachment and Emotional intelligence in the sampled organizations. We further pore over that Emotional intelligence considerably partially mediates the link between self-efficacy and psychological detachment as well as between learning goal orientation and psychological detachment.

Keywords: Self-Efficacy, Psychological Detachment, Learning Goal Orientation, Emotional intelligence.

INTRODUCTION

Self-efficacy is the trust we have in our own capacities, definitely our ability to happen the task ahead of us and a comprehensive task magnificently. General Self-efficacy refer to our overall trust in our abilities succeed. Self-efficacy depends on various factors which affects it positively and negatively with reference to human behavior and performance against a specific goal. Emotional intelligence and psychological detachments are major determents of self-efficacy. Previous studies noticed that there is a mechanism that played a huge role in people's lives that up to that idea, had not been really been defined or thoroughly practical. This device was beliefs that people have in their capacity to influence the events of their own survives. But these capacity may differ from person to person and most importantly working environment and level of Emotional Intelligence. Boyatzis et al., (2002) explain self-efficacy as the base of human action unless people believe that they can produce desire effects and anticipate undesired once by their activities, they have little motivation to act. One zone of the previous research has claimed that employees goals and emotions directly contribute to organization performance (Batool, 2013; Lakshmi & Rao, 2018) while other studies reveal an indirect path (Shariq et al.,2019; Lee 2019; Ding & Liu, 2019).

By now, it is well established that employees with sufficient salary, reward and promotion are more interested in doing job and the assigned task (Froese et al., 2019; Alhmoud & Rjoub, 2019). However, rare evidence exist on the factors that enhance psychological detachment of the employees. Particularly, despite a significant role, psychological factors of the employees are rarely touched in educational sector. Some of the studies have attempted the determinants of psychological detachment (Ng & Wang, 2019; Germeys & De Gieter, 2018) but the role of self-efficacy and learning goal orientation in psychological detachment through emotional intelligence has been ignored. In the previous studies the link found between self-efficacy and emotional intelligence but the other component like psychological detachments and learning goal orientation were not studied and correlate with each other. The given theoretical background portrays a refine image

and at the same time define the true importance of topic. Some of the studies have also scrutinized the influence of self-efficacy on psychological detachment (Sonnetag & Krueger, 2006; Clauss et al., 2018) and some studies have claimed that there is association between learning goal orientation and psychological detachment (Clinton et al., 2017; Weigelt et al., 2019). However, it is not yet known how emotional intelligence affects the path between self-efficacy and PSD as well as between learning goal orientation and PSD. The reasons behind testing the mediating role of emotional intelligence are the suggestions of recent scholars and perceived association and importance.

Additionally, Diedericks et al., (2019) also revealed that learning goal orientation displays a favorable link with psychological detachment but the link is not always direct, there are other factors that can disturb the association (Weigelt et al., 2019; Shariq et al., 2019) and Esmaeilikia, and Groth, (2019) also argued that that emotional factors of employees can affect the path between their efficacy, learning goal and psychological factors. Considering the evidence and claims of the previous studies, we use emotional intelligence as a mediator between self-efficacy and PSD as well as between learning goal orientation and PSD. In the competitive and dynamic environment, organizations face numerous challenges and constraints that hinder their profitability and survival (Thompson et al., 2019). In response to the dynamic markets and challenges, some of the organizations believe to invest in tangible resources while others firms rely on intangible means (Tian & Robertson, 2019; Monteiro, et al., 2019). In educational sector, if teachers are psychologically relaxed, they will love their job and will take interest in teaching. In results, students will take interest in learning and studying that will enhance their academic performance. Despite several strategies, it is not yet recognized in the educational sector how self-efficacy and learning goal orientation influence psychological detachment of the teachers and how emotional intelligence mediates the association. The present study advances our understanding about the psychological issue of teachers in private schools of Pakistan. This research encourages top management team and HR managers to promote employees self-efficacy and learning goal orientation in their organizations to endure psychological detachment. Further implications have stated.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Self-Efficacy and Psychological Detachment

Self-efficacy knowing is about societies' self-beliefs to switch over their implementing and actions that affect their way of life (Bandura 1994). According to Shunk and Pajars (2010), self-efficacy is self-perceptions that individuals maintain about their skills. Hopla (2014) hypothesized that self-efficacy marks choice of actions, strength, determination, and success. Linked with individuals who distrust their abilities, those with high self-efficacy for achieving a duty join more eagerly, work harder, continue lengthier when they meet difficulties, and complete at an advanced level. People achieve evidence to regulate self-efficacy from their actions, observational meetings, types of opinions, and physical replies. One's activities offer effective books for assessing self-efficacy. Attainments growth success and problems lower it, but once a solid sense of efficiency is developed failing may not have much effect (Hopla, 2014). An instructor's logic of efficiency has been starting to be connected with learner features such as inspiration, attainment, and efficiency (Tschannen-Moran et al, 1998).

Starting with the investigation on success stories, some sources of the study appeared on the results of self-regulatory processes on performance (Locke & Latham, 1990, 2002). Initial effort on aim setting construct directed on the implication of many objective options on performance, regularly representing the progressive results of launching inspiring and precise aims along with reviews (Austin & Vancouver, 1996). Effectiveness values connected with past experiences repercussions, impact the failing or achievements standing within the future and consequently impact the tutorial inspiration. Clauss et al., (2018) claimed that self-efficacy is significantly associated with psychological detachment. Moreover, Sonnetag and Krueger (2006) also confirmed a positive association between self-efficacy and psychological detachment.

A recent study was conducted by Clauss, Hoppe, Schachler, and O'Shea (2020), demonstrates that the self-efficacy of employees enhances their Psychological detachment. In a similar vein, Tement, Zorjan, Lavrič, Poštuvan, and Plohl, (2020) claimed that Employees who have high self-efficacy are most likely to be psychologically detached as compared to those employees who have low self-efficacy. This notion is also supported by the study conducted by Ahmed, Ishak, and Kamil, (2021).

H1: Self-efficacy has significant positive influence on Psychological detachment

Learning Goal Orientation and Psychological Detachment

Objective connotation relates to how entities describe and effort for attainment. Persons with pronounced wisdom goal alignment often effort to get expertise or mission in a struggle to surge ability, while those with highest rated goal alignment emphasize more rapidly on showing their capacity through discussion efficiency objects (Nicolls, 1975,1984). Certainly, learning goal orientation marks in advanced levels of demonstration than PGO (Zajac, 1996), likely due to the fact that learning goal orientation is related with more real self-parameter tactics and superior on mission consideration (Kanfr, 1990; Payne et al., 2007). For example, Heslin and Latham (2004) found that learning goal orientation implicitly expected exclusive enactment. For our conceptualization of emotional intelligence, we concentrate on those factors of this design that appear to be most essential within our structure that is learning goal orientation. These consist of perceiving feelings (Mayer & Salovey 2010), showing emotions (knowledge about emotions, information about the causes of feelings, their symptoms and results, as we have information about techniques of feelings control, and handling one's feelings meaning of being able to control them. Emotional detachment is an individual's meet of being psychologically away from accomplishing, to make a stop in considering work associated complications, therefore to "switch off". Clinton et al., (2017) scrutinized that learning goal orientation significantly enhances psychological detachment. Similarly Weigelt et al., (2019), Muñoz-García, and Villena-Martínez, (2021) also supports the above results and suggested that there is a significant association between learning goal orientation and psychological detachment. In addition, Greenier et al., (2021) concluded that learning goal orientation is significantly associated with psychological detachment.

H2: Learning goal orientation significant positive influence on Psychological detachment

Self-efficacy and Emotional intelligence:

Self-Efficacy is positively related to Emotional Intelligence. It is assumed that emotional intelligence will increase the self-efficacy and that self-efficacy will support the development of emotional intelligence (Scott, Taylor, 2017). Initially, the emotional intelligence that was considered as a sub-dimension of public intellect, in the further study has been recommended as a wide type of intellect that also takes the public intellect into (Salovey & Mayer, 1997).

Self-efficacy that appeared with the public studying concept for the first time can be labeled as the personal decision about how well the individual act in distributing with imaginable circumstances (Bandura, 1982). Academic self-efficacy perception is about how range an individual feels in finishing the educational tasks successfully. Students' aims, inspiration levels, educational achievements impact their adequacy values in learning and getting greater educational achievements (Schunk, 2009). Cox, J. D. (2011) stated that self-efficacy values have four main sources. These are immediate encounters and oblique encounters provided by social or models, spoken conviction, and individuals' psychological and physical circumstances. Black, et al., (2019), found that self-efficacy significantly enhances emotional intelligence. Additionally, Huerta et al., (2017) concluded that self-efficacy is significantly linked with emotional intelligence. In this study, it is being inspected that how emotional intelligence and self-efficacy, can be a predictor of their academic achievements.

A recent study conducted by Zheng, et al., (2021), demonstrates that self-efficacy of employees enhances their emotional intelligence at the workplace. For instance, Alessandri et al. (2021), claimed that Employees who have self-efficacy are most likely to perform well as compared to those employees who have less innovative capabilities and low emotional intelligence. For instance, Alipour, et al., (2020) also support the above notion.

H3: self-efficacy significant positive influence on Emotional intelligence.

Learning Goal Orientation and Emotional Intelligence:

According to this model, emotionally intelligent behavior means applying one's mind for perceiving and showing on learning goal orientation and controlling these feelings in a goal-directed way. Understanding symbolizes the recognition of one's feelings related to learning goal orientation. Thiptanamane and Ussahawanitchakit (2016) found that LGO significantly enhances emotional intelligence. Mison and Hee (2021) scrutinized that learning goal orientation significantly enhances employee emotional intelligence. Similarly, Rivera-Pérez et al., (2021) also support the above results and suggested that learning orientation significantly improves emotional intelligence.

H4: Learning Goal Orientation has significant positive influence on Emotional intelligence.

Emotional Intelligence and Psychological Detachment

Emotional Intelligence is a word formed by two researchers – Peter Salovey & John Mayer – and encouraged by Dan Goleman in his 1996 book of the same name. We describe emotional intelligence as the aptitude to identify, appreciate and accomplish our personal feelings. Identify, recognize, and inspire the feelings of others. In the opinion of rising effective trend in social and business mindset, emotional intelligence is measured to be playing a major part in the workplace (Kaftsiotis & Zamptakis, 2008). Following the present literature (Mayer & Salovey, 1995), emotional intelligence is measured to be composed of one's ability to identify as emotional acknowledgment and control emotions as emotional regulation (Reus & Liu, 2004). Scientists mainly recommend that such capability can guess effort-relevant results, such as job fulfillment and job efficiency (Sy et al., 2006). Interpersonally, feelings consideration and regulating processes linked with emotional intelligence are compulsory to help individuals' social networks hence impacting the practice of styles and pressure at work. The use of emotional state and knowledge of one's moods can bring about directing stress and opposing moods so that one can implement better at work (Kaftsiotis & Zamptakis, 2008). Thus theories of emotion in organizations advise that emotional conditions at work are key variables of performance and administrative impacts on job fulfillment.

Story and Castanheira (2019) argued that the emotional intelligence of employees significantly influences psychological detachment. In a similar vein, Mellner (2019) also argued that emotional intelligence is a vital predictor of and psychological detachment. Many researchers argue that emotional intelligence leads to higher psychological detachment (Kaur & Hirudayaraj, 2021; Pellegrini et al., 2021). A recent study conducted in Pakistani context by Naeem et al., (2021) also concluded that emotional intelligence if employees significantly associated with psychological detachment.

H5: Emotional intelligence has significant positive influence on Psychological detachment.

Mediating Role of Emotional Intelligence:

This study inspected the mediating role of Emotional Intelligence in the relationship among self-efficacy, learning goal orientation, and psychological detachment. Accessible proof indicates that protected people are relatively precise in perceiving face expression of adverse feelings, whereas avoidant people have low emotion-decoding precision ratings (Magai et al., 1995). One encounter that is necessary for regeneration to happen be emotional disinterest from work during free time. Etzon et al., (1998) referred to mental detachment as the sense of disinterest from effort routine and described it as “the person's feeling of being absent from the work situation”. It is worth noting that emotional disinterest is more than just being truly absent from businesses. Emotional disinterest demonstrates that one is not filled by work-related tasks. In addition to symbols of reduced psychological well-being, we scanned work appointments as a positive display of job-associated well-being. Devotion refers to passion, inspiration, and the involvement of significance and pride at work. Job burdens are the real, responsive, common, and business features of a job that require normal actual, intellectual, and emotional struggle and skills (Demrouti et al., 2001). In unity with past conceptualizations of work necessities, we targeted measurable necessities that proposed a great amount of work and time burden (De Lang et al., 2003). Emotional disinterest communicates to an “entity's feeling of being absent from the work position” (Etzon et al., 1998).

Moreover, protected people are less confronted by possibly upsetting information; they can brand, skill, and show experienced feelings; when under pressure, they search for support as a feeling control technique and use flexible and efficient techniques (Larose et al., 1999). Kim et al., (2019) scrutinized that self-efficacy also affects the mental behaviors of the employees and there is a need to assess the relationship further. Similarly, Ebert et al., 2015 and Clayton et al., (2015) claimed that the path between self-efficacy and psychological detachment can be affected by several factors. Diedericks et al., (2019) also revealed that learning goal orientation displays a favorable link with psychological detachment but the link is not always direct, other factors can disturb the association (Weigelt et al., 2019; Shariq et al., 2019) and Esmaeilikia, and Groth, (2019) also argued that emotional factors of employees can affect the path between their efficacy, learning goal and psychological factors. Considering the evidence and claims of the previous studies, we use

emotional intelligence as a mediator between self-efficacy and Psychological detachment as well as between learning goal orientation and Psychological detachment.

H6: Emotional intelligence significantly mediates the relationship between Self-efficacy and Psychological detachment.

H7: Emotional intelligence significantly mediates the relationship between: Learning goal orientation and Psychological detachment.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To examine the influence of self-efficacy on psychological detachment

To examine the impact of learning goal orientation on psychological detachment

To test if self-efficacy influence emotional intelligence

To assess the influence of learning goal orientation on emotional intelligence

To measure the impact of emotional intelligence on psychological detachment.

To unleash if emotional intelligence mediates the path between self-efficacy and PSD

To examine if the association between learning goal orientation and PSD is mediated by the emotional intelligence of the school teachers.

COCEPTUAL FRAMWORK

METHODOLOGY

In this research, the data was collected through a structured questioner from the academic sector in Pakistan and focused on the mental satisfaction of teachers and Principals. Because in this particular institution management focuses on self-efficacy and also learning goal orientation, this research focuses on learning goal orientation and its impact on psychology detachment with mediating role of Emotional intelligence. Through convenient sampling, the data was collected from the education sectors in Pakistan, among the total usable responses 243(70%) were used through the quantitative research methodology, 5-point Likert scale, and interpreted result through SPSS. There are numerous statistical tools used to examine the data. In the first place, factor analysis would be conducted. Descriptive statistics were conducted to assess the regression, frequency table, and correlation. The correlation was tested to find out the relationship magnitude of variables. The calculation summary is in the following tables.

Table 1 Demographics of the participants

Particular	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	148	60.9
Female	95	39.1
Experience		

	1-5	39	16.0
	6-10	102	42.0
	11-15	46	18.9
	16-20	36	14.8
	21-25	12	4.9
	26-30	8	3.3
Age	20-25	35	14.4
	26-30	104	19.8
	31-35	48	42.8
	36-40	36	14.8
	41-45	12	4.9
	46-50	8	3.3
Marital status	Single	142	41.4
	Married	101	58.6
Income	20000-40000	64	26.3
	41000-60000	91	37.4
	61000-80000	70	28.8
	81000 and above	18	7.4
Education	Undergraduate	58	23.9
	Graduate	156	64.2
	Postgraduate	29	11.9

Table 1 shows the details of employees who participate in this research. Total 243 employees participate in this research. Most of the participants were male, extreme respondents lie between the age group 31-35, married, between 41000 to 60000 income level, and graduate.

Reliability Analysis

The below table represents the alpha reliability of different variables. All the variables have Cronbach's alpha in acceptable threshold level (greater than 0.70). Additionally, alpha reliability value for self-efficacy ($\alpha= 0.968$), learning goal orientation ($\alpha= 0.826$), emotional intelligence is ($\alpha= 0.883$) and psychological detachment (0.697).

Table 2: Reliability Analysis:

	No of items	Alpha reliability
SE	10	0.968
LGO	8	0.826
EI	16	0.883
PSD	4	0.697

Note: SE=Self-efficacy, LGO=Learning goal orientation, EI=Emotional intelligence, PSD= Psychological Detachment

Descriptive statistics:

The below table reported the normality and descriptive state of the main variable of the study along with the Skewness and kurtosis. The mean value and standard deviation values of all the variables such as the mean and standard deviation value for self-efficacy (M=3.51, STD=0.61), for learning goal orientation (M=3.70, STD=0.036), for emotional intelligence (M=3.71, STD=0.33) and for Psychological Detachment (M=3.67, STD=0.038). Furthermore, the mean value ranges from lower 3.51 (self-efficacy) up to high 3.71(emotional intelligence). While the standard deviation value ranges from 0.33 (emotional intelligence) up to high 0.61 (self-efficacy). The data is normal because the Skewness and kurtosis values are in the range of +/-2 as suggested by George (2011).

Table 3: Descriptive statistics:

	Mean(M)	Std. Deviation(STD)	Skewness	Kurtosis
SE	3.5198	0.61249	-0.936	0.962
LGO	3.7099	0.36266	-1.300	1.001
EI	3.7101	0.33470	-1.112	1.588
PSD	3.6739	0.38484	-1.651	1.740

Note: SE=Self-efficacy, LGO=Learning goal orientation, EI=Emotional intelligence, PSD=Psychological Detachment.

Correlation analysis

To test the association between the main constructs of the study Pearson correlation coefficient has been used in SPSS. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) values of the main constructs of the study are reported below table. All the relationships between constructs are highly significant and in the acceptable range. The results show that SE (self-efficacy) and LGO learning goal orientation) are significantly related with PSD (Psychological Detachment) ($r=0.377^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), ($r=0.381^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). Similarly SE and LGO are significantly related with EI (Emotional intelligence) ($r=0.304^{**}$, $p < 0.01$), ($r=0.401^{**}$, $p < 0.01$). Furthermore, EI is significantly linked with PSD ($r=0.396^{**}$, $p < 0.01$).

Table 4: Correlation analysis:

	Exp	Age	Income	Education	SE	LGO	EI	PSD
Experience	1							
Age	0.190**	1						
Income	0.057	0.128*	1					
Education	0.127*	0.127*	0.093	1				
SE	0.023	0.008	0.047	0.053	1			
LGO	-0.058	-0.076	0.084	-0.107	0.338**	1		
EI	0.031	-0.001	0.036	-0.039	0.304**	0.401**	1	
PSD	-0.035	-0.075	0.008	-0.059	0.377**	0.381**	0.396**	1

Note: SE=Self-efficacy, LGO=Learning goal orientation, EI=Emotional intelligence, PSD= Psychological Detachment, **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). *. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Regression analysis

The below table 5, table 6, table 7, and table 8 below report the regression results. In order to test the mediating role of Emotional intelligence between self-efficacy and psychological detachment, as well as between learning goal orientation and psychological detachment Baron and Kenny's (1986) four steps method has been used.

Table 5 shows the first step result in which SE (self-efficacy) and LGO (learning goal orientation) were regressed on PSD (Psychological Detachment). The results (see table 5) indicate that SE ($\beta = 0.180$, $t = 4.66$, $p < 0.01$) and LGO ($\beta = 0.295$, $t = 4.47$, $P < 0.01$) significantly influence PSD which strongly supports H1 and H2 of the study. The R square value shows that SE and LGO both explain 21.1 percent variation in PSD. Similarly, table 6 shows the second step result in which SE (self-efficacy) and LGO (learning goal orientation) were regressed on EI (Emotional intelligence). The results of table 6 reveal that SE ($\beta = 0.104$, $t = 3.0466$, $p < 0.01$) and LGO ($\beta = 0.313$, $t = 5.37$, $P < 0.01$) significantly influence EI which strongly substantiate H3 and H24 of the study. The R square value shows that SE and LGO both explain a 19.1 percent variation in EI. To substantiate hypothesis 5 (see table 7) in the third step EI (Emotional intelligence) was regressed on PSD (psychological detachment). The results of table 7 displayed that EI significantly influences PSD ($\beta = 0.355$, $t = 3.04$, $p < 0.01$) which supports H 5 of the study. The results of table 8 show the mediating role of Emotional intelligence. The outcomes in table 8 indicate that the direct effect of SE and LGO on PSD are significant ($\beta = 0.151$, $t = 3.94$, $p < 0.05$), ($\beta = 0.207$, $t = 3.05$, $p < 0.051$) and the indirect effect of SE and LGO on PSD (via Emotional intelligence) has also remained significant ($\beta = 0.282$, $t = 3.94$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that Emotional intelligence partially mediates the relationship between self-efficacy and psychological detachment, as well as between learning goal orientation and psychological detachment. Henceforth it's partially favoring the H6 and H7. Furthermore, the coefficient of determination (R square) describes that 26.8% variance in psychological detachment was brought by between self-efficacy and learning goal orientation in the presence of Emotional intelligence.

Table 5: Relationship of SE and LGO with PSD:

	B	t-value	p-value	R square	R square change	F significance
Mode 1						
(Constant)	3.784	34.234	0.000	0.009		
Exp	-0.005	-0.256	0.798			
Age	-0.021	-1.028	0.305			
Income	0.010	0.347	0.729			
Education	-0.033	-0.760	0.448			
Model 2						
(Constant)	2.053	7.910	0.000	0.220	0.211	0.000
Exp	-0.003	-0.187	0.852			

Age	-0.015	-0.795	0.427
Income	-0.008	-0.321	0.748
Education	-0.023	-0.587	0.558
SE	0.180	4.664	0.000
LGO	0.295	4.477	0.000

Table 6: Relationship of SE and LGO with EI:

	B	t-value	p-value	R square	R square change	F significance
Mode 1						
(Constant)	3.708	38.479	.000	0.004		
Exp	0.010	.539	.590			
Age	-0.002	-.103	.918			
Income	0.015	.605	.546			
education	-0.026	-.701	.484			
Model 2						
(Constant)	2.164	9.442	0.000	0.196	0.191	0.000
Exp	0.012	0.759	0.448			
Age	0.005	0.296	0.767			
Income	-0.002	-0.069	0.945			
education	-0.011	-0.333	0.740			
SE	0.104	3.041	0.003			
LGO	0.313	5.377	0.000			

Table 7: Relationship of EI with PSD:

	B	t-value	p-value	R square	R square change	F significance
Mode 1						
(Constant)	3.784	38.479	0.000	0.009		
Exp	-0.005	0.539	0.590			
Age	-0.021	-0.103	0.918			
Income	0.010	0.605	0.546			
education	-0.033	-0.701	0.484			
Model 2						
(Constant)	2.097	9.442	0.000	0.165	0.156	0.000
Exp	-0.010	0.759	0.448			
Age	-0.021	0.296	0.767			
Income	0.003	-0.069	0.945			
education	-0.021	-0.333	0.740			
EI	0.455	3.041	0.003			

Table 8: Mediating role of EI:

	B	t-value	p-value	R square	R square change	F significance
Mode 1						
(Constant)	3.784	34.234	0.000	0.009		
Exp	-0.005	-0.256	0.798			
Age	-0.021	-1.028	0.305			
Income	0.010	0.347	0.729			
education	-0.033	-0.760	0.448			
Model 2						
(Constant)	2.053	7.910	0.000	0.220	0.211	0.000
Exp	-0.003	-0.187	0.852			
Age	-0.015	-0.795	0.427			
Income	-0.008	-0.321	0.748			
education	-0.023	-0.587	0.558			
SE	0.180	4.664	0.000			
LGO	0.295	4.477	0.000			
Model 3						
(Constant)	1.443	4.879	0.000	0.268	0.048	0.000
Exp	-0.007	-0.387	0.699			
Age	-0.016	-0.895	0.371			
Income	-0.008	-0.313	0.754			
education	-0.019	-0.519	0.604			
SE	0.151	3.948	0.000			
LGO	0.207	3.052	0.003			
EI	0.282	3.943	0.000			

Mediation role of Emotional intelligence between SE and PSD

The table 9 shows that SE significantly influence both PSD ($\beta = 0.237$, $t=6.32$) and EI ($\beta = 0.16$, $t=4.95$). Similarly, EI significantly influences PSD ($\beta = 0.35$, $t=5.21$). To test the mediating role of EI between SE

and PSD, the PROCESS method in SPSS has been executed. The results (see table 9) shown that both the direct effect and indirect effect of SE on PSD were significant ($\beta = 0.17, t = 4.75, p < 0.05$), ($\beta = 0.0593, p < 0.05$). The result shows that EI plays a partial mediating role in SE and PSD nexus. Additionally the outcomes of the Normal theory test ($\beta = 0.0593, p < 0.5, z = 3.56$) and method of bootstrap at 95% level of (LL=.124, UL=.154) confidence interval also revealed that the EI partially mediates the SE and PSD nexus. The value of R square describes that 22% in PSD was brought by SE in the presence of EI.

Table 9: Results for mediation role of Emotional intelligence:

Direct and total effect					
Dependent: PSD(Y), Independent: SE (X) Mediator: EI (M)					
Total effect and Direct effect	β	SE	p	t	R ²
Part1: Outcome EI (effect of X on M)					
SE	0.16	0.03	.000	4.95	0.09
Part2: Outcome PSD (effect of M and X on Y)	β	SE	p	t	R ²
EI	0.35	0.06	0.00	5.21	
SE	0.17	0.03	0.00	4.75	0.22
Part3: Outcome PSD (total effect model)	β	SE	p	t	
SE	0.237	0.03	0.00	6.32	0.142
indirect effect					
Normal theory/Sobel test	β	SE	P	Z	
SE→ EI→ PSD	0.0593	0.0167	0.00	3.567	
indirect effect (Bootstrap method)					
Bootstrapping	Indirect effects	LLCI at95%		ULCI	
SE→ EI→ PSD	.0593	.0124		At95% 0.154	

Note: N=243, 2,000-bootstrapping sample size, LLCI = Lower Limit Confidence Interval confidence interval, ULCI=Upper Limit Confidence Interval, DEP=Dependent variable INDV= Independent variables, MEDIV=Mediating variable SE=Self-efficacy, PSD= Psychological detachment, EI=Emotional intelligence.

Mediation role of Emotional intelligence between LGO and PSD

The table 10 shows that LGO significantly influence both PSD ($\beta = 0.40, t = 6.40$) and EI ($\beta = 0.37, t = 6.79$). Similarly, EI significantly influences PSD ($\beta = .33, t = 6.64$). To examine the mediating role of EI between LGO and PSD, the PROCESS method in SPSS has been executed. The results (see table 11) showed that both the direct effect and indirect effect of LGO on PSD were significant ($\beta = 0.28, t = 4.24, p < 0.05$), ($\beta = 0.123, p < 0.05$). The result shows that EI plays a partial mediating role in LGO and PSD nexus. Additionally the outcomes of the Normal theory test ($\beta = 0.123, p < 0.5, z = 3.80$) and method of bootstrap at 95% level of (LL=.323, UL=.275) confidence interval also revealed that the EI partially mediates the LGO and PSD nexus. The value of R square describes that 21% in PSD was brought by LGO in the presence of EI.

Table 10: Results for mediation role of Emotional intelligence:

Direct and total effect					
Dependent: PSD(Y), Independent: LGO (X) Mediator: EI (M)					
Total effect and Direct effect	β	SE	p	t	R ²
Part1: Outcome EI (effect of X on M)					
SE	0.37	0.05	.000	6.79	0.16
Part2: Outcome PSD (effect of M and X on Y)	β	SE	p	t	R ²
EI	0.33	0.07	0.00	4.64	
LGO	0.28	0.06	0.00	4.24	0.21
Part3: Outcome PSD (total effect model)	β	SE	p	t	
LGO	0.40	0.06	0.00	6.4	0.14
indirect effect					
Normal theory/Sobel test	β	SE	P	z	
LGO→ EI→ PSD	0.123	0.03	0.00	3.809	
indirect effect (Bootstrap method)					
Bootstrapping	Indirect effects	LLCI at95%		ULCI	
LGO→ EI→ PSD	.123	.0323		At95% 0.275	

Note: N=243, 2,000-bootstrapping sample size, LLCI = Lower Limit Confidence Interval confidence interval, ULCI=Upper Limit Confidence Interval, DEP=Dependent variable INDV= Independent variables, MEDIV=Mediating variable, PSD = Psychological detachment, LGO=Learning goal orientation, EI=Emotional intelligence.

Hypotheses	Remarks
H1: Self-efficacy has significant positive influence on Psychological detachment.	Accepted
H2: Learning goal orientation significant positive influence on Psychological detachment	Accepted
H3: Self-efficacy has significant positive influence on Emotional intelligence.	Accepted
H4: Learning goal orientation significant positive influence on Emotional intelligence	accepted
H5: Emotional intelligence has significant positive influence on Psychological detachment.	Accepted
H6: Emotional intelligence significantly mediates the relationship between Self-efficacy and Psychological detachment.	Partially accepted
H7: Emotional intelligence significantly mediates the relationship between: Learning goal orientation and Psychological detachment.	Partially accepted

Discussion

The main theme of this research is to check the mediating role of EI between SE and PSD as well as between LGO and PSD among the staff of educational institutions of Pakistan. Though, previous studies have been made significant contributions to the body of knowledge related to EI, SE, and LGO in both Europe and Asian literature (Huerta et al., 2017; Ordun, & Akün, 2017; Shariq et al., 2019). Both theoretical and empirical studies have been carried out forward to assess the importance of SE and LGO in PSD (Zhang et al., 2017; Clauss et al., 2018; Sonnentag, & Krueger, 2006). However, several constraints are found in the published literature such as lack of applicability in research, fragmented results, and lack of theoretical underpinning. However, our research aims to possibly overcome the constraints and advance the understanding of the existing theory of goal orientation and theory of self-efficacy. However, little attention is given to the theory of goal orientation (Kaplan & Maehr, 2007) in the educational sector. Goal orientation theory states how people achieve their objectives by connecting emotionally and physically (Anderman & Maehr, 1994). Our research also tests the self-efficacy theory (Bandura & Adams, 1977) which states that efficacy affects people's actions and behavioral settings. The higher the efficacy, the more they will be able to cope with their surroundings. It is doubtless that both the theories have been received considerable attention from empirical and conceptual research. However, these theories have been neglected in empirical studies of emerging organizations. Especially, the educational sector of emerging areas has been given minor attention in the scope of both theories. Hence, our study sheds light on the importance of goal orientation and self-efficacy theories through an empirical way and revealed that the theory plays an important role in the educational sector. To shrink the theoretical contribution, our research extends the scope of goal orientation theory and self-efficacy in an empirical way towards the literature of emotional intelligence and PSD as well to the educational sector. Our study has unpacked worthy results that are discussed below.

We found that SE significantly and positively contributes to PSD in the educational sector of emerging markets. Our results match with the prior work of (Clauss, Hoppe & Schachner, 2018) who claimed that self-efficacy significantly enhanced psychological detachment. For instance, Sonnentag and Krueger (2006) also confirmed a positive association between self-efficacy and psychological detachment. Which favored H1 Furthermore, we found that LGO significantly influences PSD. Our results are matched with the studies where Clinton, Conway, and Sturges, (2017) as well as Weigelt, Gierer and Syrek, (2019) resulted in a favorable association between LGO and PSD. Secondly, this study concluded that self-efficacy and learning goal orientation significantly influence emotional intelligence and support H3 and H4. These outcomes are in line with previous studies of Ordun and Akün, (2017) confirmed that SE and EI are significantly linked. The results are also Consistent with Min (2017) who demonstrated that SE and EI have a linear association. Furthermore Thiptanamanee and Ussahawanitchakit (2016). Suggested that LGO significantly enhances EI. Consistent with Babalola (2016) who carried out a study in Europe and demonstrated that job satisfaction and job commitment go in a parallel and have a linear association. Similarly, Story and Castanheira (2019) also argued that job satisfaction is a vital predictor of employee commitment. Thirdly this study reveals that the emotional intelligence of employees significantly influences psychological detachment which favored H5. This result is consistent with the outcomes of Consistent with Yeh (2018) who carried out a study in Taiwan and demonstrated that emotional intelligence and psychological detachment have a significant linear

association. Similarly, Mellner (2019) also argued that emotional intelligence is a vital predictor of and psychological detachment. Lastly, this study revealed that emotional intelligence partially mediates the nexus between self-efficacy and psychological detachment and as well the relationship between learning goal orientation psychological detachment. which supported H6 and H7. these results are matched with the study of Weigelt, Gierer, and Syrek (2019) who claimed that emotional intelligence significantly affects the paths between efficacy, psychological factor, our study revealed that emotional intelligence plays a partial role. Similarly, our results partially support Shariq, Mukhtar, and Anwar (2019) and Esmaeilikia and Groth (2019) who scrutinized that emotional factors of employees can affect the path between learning goal orientation and psychological factors.

Implications for Practice

This research has several substitutional implications for educational institutions, educational organizations, policymakers, and practitioners that are discussed below. Our research revealed that self-efficacy has a significant influence on PSD. Hence, we recommend employees emphasize their efficacy in order to detach themselves from the work in off time. This study also unleashed that learning goal orientation is a significant predictor of PSD. Therefore, employees need to learn their goals and objectives, so they will have a level of psychological attachment with their work during off time. We found self-efficiency and learning goal orientation improve emotional intelligence among employees. Hence, employees need to focus on emotional intelligence through improving self-efficacy and learning goal orientation. Our results display that emotional intelligence also facilitates employees in detachment from work. Therefore, it is suggested for the employees and especially educational institutions to configure their emotional intelligence abilities. We revealed that emotional intelligence partially mediates the path between self-efficacy and PSD. In other words, we can state that self-efficacy is equally important for emotional intelligence and PSD in the educational sector. We also scrutinized that emotional intelligence partially affects the link between learning goal orientation and PSD among the educational staff. Therefore, our results suggest that employees should consider self-efficacy and learning goal orientation equally important for emotional intelligence and PSD. current research suggests educational staff emphasize self-efficacy, learning goal orientation, and emotional intelligence in order to enhance their PSD because too much attachment with work can cause a mental problem. Educational staff often face mental pressure during work and duty. Therefore, it is also suggested for heads and principals to take care of their employees to gain desired outcomes. Our research recommends educational staff and policymakers focus on working conditions and environment in order to improve the efficiency of educational employees and teachers. The findings of this research are not confined to the emerging market of Pakistan. However, the attached neighboring countries can implement these implications in their educational sectors. Moreover, educational staff can opt for these implications for their better psychological outcomes.

Limitation and Future Direction:

We have tried to avoid constraints but still, there are a few limitations that need to be addressed. The first limitation of this research is emphasizing the educational sector of Pakistan. We advise future researchers to consider other sectors such as business and social and conduct surveys in manufacturing, trading, and NPOs in order to gain worthy information. The second limitation of this research is using a structured questionnaire for testing the hypotheses. We suggest an in-depth interview with a few responsible managers to reduce the chance of common method biases. Third, we tested the hypotheses using the regression model in SPSS that may not be a good approach in the case of mediators. Therefore, we suggest AMOS and PROCESS in future work to enhance the validity of the model. Moreover, we advise a comparative study on empirical evidence between Asian and European organizations to generate worthy implications for both organizations. Regarding the model, we suggest other moderators and mediators articulate the results in a better pattern. Hence, similar to innovation, perhaps mediating role of creativity can provide good results to check the direct and indirect path.

Conclusion

Based on the theories of goal orientation and self-efficacy, our research unpacks the importance of self-efficacy and learning goal orientation in PSD through emotional intelligence as a mediator. To test the hypothesized model, we collected evidence through a structured questionnaire from 243 educational employees of Pakistani institutions. We used SPSS to test the hypotheses and generate results. Our results

displayed that self-efficacy and learning goal orientation is very important for PSD and both are also very vital for emotional intelligence. We also revealed that emotional intelligence has a significant influence on PSD. However, we scrutinized that emotional intelligence plays a partial mediating role between self-efficacy and PSD as well as between learning goal orientation and PSD. Our research recommends educational staff and policymakers focus on working conditions and environment in order to improve the efficiency of educational employees and teachers.

References:

- i. Ahmed, O. M., Ishak, A. K., & Kamil, B. A. M. (2021). Academics' life satisfaction: the role of perceived stress, organisational justice and self-efficacy. *International Journal of Management in Education*, 15(1), 1-22.
- ii. Alessandri, G., Filosa, L., Eisenberg, N., & Caprara, G. V. (2021). Within-Individual Relations of Emotional, Social, and Work Self-Efficacy Beliefs to Organizational Citizenship Behaviors. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 104073.
- iii. Alipour, M., Mousavi, P., Afshary, P., & Hossein, M. (2020). The relationship of emotional intelligence with self-efficacy in midwives working in maternity blocks in Khuzestan. *Journal of Advanced Pharmacy Education & Research* | Oct-Dec, 10(4), 111.
- iv. Anderman, E. M., & Maehr, M. L. (1994). Motivation and schooling in the middle grades. *Review of Educational Research*, 64(2), 287-309.
- v. Bakker, A. B., Petrou, P., Den Kamp, E. M. O., & Tims, M. (2020). Proactive vitality management, work engagement, and creativity: The role of goal orientation. *Applied Psychology*, 69(2), 351-378.
- vi. Bandura, A., & Adams, N. E. (1977). Analysis of self-efficacy theory of behavioral change. *Cognitive therapy and research*, 1(4), 287-310.
- vii. Batool, B. F. (2013). Emotional intelligence and effective leadership. *Journal of business studies quarterly*, 4(3), 84.
- viii. Black, J., Kim, K., Rhee, S., Wang, K., & Sakchutchawan, S. (2019). Self-efficacy and emotional intelligence. *Team Performance Management: An International Journal*.
- ix. Boyatzis, R. E., Stubbs, E. C., & Taylor, S. N. (2002). Learning cognitive and emotional intelligence competencies through graduate management education. *Academy of Management Learning & Education*, 1(2), 150-162.
- x. Carmeli, A. (2003). The relationship between emotional intelligence and work attitudes, behavior and outcomes: An examination among senior managers. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 18(8), 788-813.
- xi. Clauss, E., Hoppe, A., Schachler, V., & O'Shea, D. (2020). Occupational self-efficacy and work engagement as moderators in the stressor-detachment model. *Work & Stress*, 1-19.
- xii. Clayton, R. W., Thomas, C. H., Singh, B., & Winkel, D. E. (2015). Exercise as a means of reducing perceptions of work-family conflict: A test of the roles of self-efficacy and psychological strain. *Human Resource Management*, 54(6), 1013-1035.
- xiii. Clinton, M. E., Conway, N., & Sturges, J. (2017). "It's tough hanging-up a call": The relationships between calling and work hours, psychological detachment, sleep quality, and morning vigor. *Journal of occupational health psychology*, 22(1), 28.
- xiv. Ebert, D. D., Berking, M., Thiart, H., Riper, H., Laferton, J. A., Cuijpers, P., ... & Lehr, D. (2015). Restoring depleted resources: Efficacy and mechanisms of change of an internet-based unguided recovery training for better sleep and psychological detachment from work. *Health Psychology*, 34(S), 1240.
- xv. Froese, F. J., Peltokorpi, V., Varma, A., & Hitotsuyanagi-Hansel, A. (2019). Merit-based rewards, job satisfaction and voluntary turnover: moderating effects of employee demographic characteristics. *British Journal of Management*, 30(3), 610-623.
- xvi. Germeys, L., & De Gieter, S. (2018). A diary study on the role of psychological detachment in the spillover of self-control demands to employees' ego depletion and the crossover to their partner. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 27(1), 140-152.
- xvii. Gilmore, L., & Cuskelly, M. (2012). Parenting satisfaction and self-efficacy: A longitudinal study of mothers of children with Down syndrome. *Journal of Family Studies*, 18(1), 28-35.

- xvii. Greenier, V., Derakhshan, A., & Fathi, J. (2021). *Emotion regulation and psychological well-being in teacher work engagement: A case of British and Iranian English language teachers*. *System*, 97, 102446.
- xviii. Hopla, J. J. (2014). *Self-efficacy: undergraduate program evaluation of general* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Idaho).
- xix. Huerta, M., Goodson, P., Beigi, M., & Chlup, D. (2017). *Graduate students as academic writers: writing anxiety, self-efficacy and emotional intelligence*. *Higher Education Research & Development*, 36(4), 716-729.
- xx. Kaplan, A., & Maehr, M. L. (2007). *The contributions and prospects of goal orientation theory*. *Educational psychology review*, 19(2), 141-184.
- xxi. Kim, D. H., Bassett, S. M., So, S., & Voisin, D. R. (2019). *Family stress and youth mental health problems: Self-efficacy and future orientation mediation*. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 89(2), 125.
- xxii. Lakshmi, K. N., & Rao, K. S. (2018). *A Study on Role of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Performance*. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology*, 9(3).
- xxiii. Liu, Y., & Perrewe, P. L. (2005). *Another look at the role of emotion in the organizational change: A process model*. *Human Resource Management Review*, 15(4), 263-280.
- xxiv. Mayer, J., Salovey, P., & Caruso, D. (2004). *Psychological Inquiry: An International Journal for the Advancement of Psychological Theory*. *Psychological Inquiry*, 15(3), 197-215.
- xxv. Misron, A., & Hee, O. C. (2021). *A Conceptual Analysis of Personality Traits, Emotional Intelligence and Customer-Oriented Behaviour among Malaysian Nursing Students*.
- xxvi. Monteiro, A. P., Soares, A. M., & Rua, O. L. (2019). *Linking intangible resources and entrepreneurial orientation to export performance: the mediating effect of dynamic capabilities*. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 4(3), 179-187.
- xxvii. Naeem, K., Jawad, A., Rehman, S. U., & Javaid, U. (2021). *Psychological Wellbeing, Job Burnout and Counter Productive Work Behavior among Drivers of Car Hailing Services in Pakistan: Moderating Role of Captains' Personality Traits*. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 10(1), pp-19.
- xxviii. Ng, T. W., & Wang, M. (2019). *An actor-partner interdependence model of employees' and coworkers' innovative behavior, psychological detachment, and strain reactions*. *Personnel Psychology*, 72(3), 445-476.
- xxix. Pastor, I. (2014). *Leadership and emotional intelligence: the effect on performance and attitude*. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 15, 985-992.
- xxx. Pellegrini, P. G., Tolfo, S. D. R., Bolze, S. D. A., & D'Cruz, P. (2021). *The interface between significant others and workplace bullying, emotional abuse and harassment. Pathways of Job-related Negative Behaviour*, 423-446.
- xxxi. Rivera-Pérez, S., Fernandez-Rio, J., & Iglesias Gallego, D. (2021). *Effects of an 8-Week Cooperative Learning Intervention on Physical Education Students' Task and Self-Approach Goals, and Emotional Intelligence*. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 18(1), 61.
- xxxii. Shariq, S. M., Mukhtar, U., & Anwar, S. (2019). *Mediating and moderating impact of goal orientation and emotional intelligence on the relationship of knowledge oriented leadership and knowledge sharing*. *Journal of Knowledge Management*.
- xxxiii. Shepherd, D. A., Patzelt, H., & Wolfe, M. (2011). *Moving forward from project failure: Negative emotions, affective commitment, and learning from the experience*. *Academy of Management Journal*, 54(6), 1229-1259
- xxxiv. Sonnentag, S. (2012). *Psychological detachment from work during leisure time: The benefits of mentally disengaging from work*. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 21(2), 114-118.
- xxxv. Sonnentag, S., & Krueger, U. (2006). *Psychological detachment from work during off-job time: The role of job stressors, job involvement, and recovery-related self-efficacy*. *European Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology*, 15(2), 197-217.

- xxxvi. Tement, S., Zorjan, S., Lavrič, M., Poštuvan, V., & Plohl, N. (2020). A randomized controlled trial to improve psychological detachment from work and well-being among employees: a study protocol comparing online CBT-based and mindfulness interventions. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 1-15.
- xxxvii. Thiptanamane, P., & Ussahawanitchakit, P. (2016). Learning orientation, emotional intelligence and job success: an empirical research of automobile industry in Thailand. *The Business & Management Review*, 7(5), 212.
- xxxviii. Thompson, C. L., Kuah, A. T., Foong, R., & Ng, E. S. (2019). The development of emotional intelligence, self-efficacy, and locus of control in Master of Business Administration students. *Human Resource Development Quarterly*.
- xxxix. Tian, Q., & Robertson, J. L. (2019). How and when does perceived CSR affect employees' engagement in voluntary pro-environmental behavior?. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 155(2), 399-412.
- xl. Tong, J., Chong, S., Chen, J., Johnson, R. E., & Ren, X. (2020). The Interplay of Low Identification, Psychological Detachment, and Cynicism for Predicting Counterproductive Work Behaviour. *Applied Psychology*, 69(1), 59-92. Van Dam, A., Noordzij, G., & Born, M. P. (2020). Linking the fit between achievement goal orientation and learning opportunities with employee well-being and absenteeism. *Journal of Personnel Psychology*. Z
- xli. Weigelt, O., Gierer, P., & Syrek, C. J. (2019). My Mind is Working Overtime—Towards an Integrative Perspective of Psychological Detachment, Work-Related Rumination, and Work Reflection. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(16), 2987.
- xlii. Yu, Q., Yen, D. A., Barnes, B. R., & Huang, Y. A. (2019). Enhancing firm performance through internal market orientation and employee organizational commitment. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(6), 964-987.
- xliii. Zheng, J., Zhang, Z., Wu, G., Yang, Y., Xia, N., & Liu, B. (2021). Daily Self-Efficacy, Work Engagement, and Deviance Behavior among Construction Professionals and Workers: Cross-Level Moderating Role of Job Control. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 147(4).